

Assessment Framework for Rewarding Mechanisms (MS48)

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Means of Verification

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1. Objective

1. Identify rewarding mechanisms for on-farm emissions reductions and avoidance, carbon removals and climate adaptation¹, assess their rewarding design and understand their strength and weaknesses².
 - a. Conceptual model: identify, categorise and describe rewarding mechanisms
 - b. Criteria for assessing rewarding mechanisms
 - c. Assess strength and weaknesses
2. Select and describe successful examples of rewarding mechanisms and their outcomes (case studies).
3. Provide recommendations for scaling up of rewarding mechanisms, including their combinations.
4. Interlink with task 6.3 (stakeholder needs and challenges), task 6.4 (developing capacity-building material) task 6.4 (Policy recommendations).
5. Involvement of CFD-Network especially the national coordinators through surveys.

¹ This includes all GHGs (CH₄, N₂O, CO₂)

² This does not include the supply chain

2. Introduction

This draft outline has the purpose of shaping the future work of task 6.2. and will be adapted as work in progress.

Farmers face numerous positive and negative effects on the climate and adaptiveness to climate change. Broadly speaking, policymakers and the private market can encourage farmers to take actions that increase climate change mitigation (i.e. reduce emissions or increase carbon removals) and adaptation to climate change using two categories of policy approaches: “carrots” or “sticks”. “Sticks” include quotas or quantitative limits, taxes, and regulatory requirements or bans, all of which achieve behaviour change by penalizing or making it illegal to implement unfavorable actions. Conversely, policymakers or the private market can reward farmers for implementing favourable actions, and thereby incentivise positive change – “carrots”.

In this task, we focus on these so-called “carrots”, which we refer to as rewarding mechanisms. Rewarding mechanisms for agricultural actions that reduce or avoid emissions, remove carbon from the atmosphere, adapt to climate change are defined as mechanisms that reward farmers in return for implementing a desired action or delivering a desired outcome and can be sourced from public or private entities or a mix of both. Rewarding mechanisms are typified by aiming to induce a behaviour change, the use of positive incentives, and their voluntary nature. These rewarding mechanisms can take diverse forms, including regulatory obligations (that are rewarded), voluntary public funds, R&D, voluntary carbon markets and price premiums/labelling, among others.

In the context of agriculture and climate mitigation/adaptation, a number of studies have investigated subsets of rewarding mechanisms.

In particular, we draw on the following studies to frame our evaluation:

- OECD (2019) investigate the potential for agriculture to mitigate climate change globally and model the possible impacts of a number of different policy instruments, including rewarding mechanisms. This study provides an overall framing for our evaluation of rewarding mechanisms, including the scale and potential of agricultural climate mitigation.
- Warnecke, et al (2015) provides an overview of result-based payment structures, and their strengths and weaknesses, in the context of the wider climate change mitigation discussion. ST1 (2021), COWI et al (2021) and McDonald et al (2021a) discuss result-based payments within the more specific context of farming mitigation.
- The European Commission (2021) evaluates the climate performance of the Common Agricultural Policy, Europe’s largest funder of agricultural actions. The study identifies all relevant measures for climate in the CAP 2014-2020, describing how these measures work and their impact. This study provides a useful overview of measures – including rewarding measures such as direct payments and rural development payments – that will be supplemented by studies focussed on the new CAP 2023-2027.
- I4CE (2019) and McDonald et al (2021b) focus on voluntary carbon market approaches to reward carbon farming (and other climate mitigation measures).
- McDonald, H., Seeger, I., Lago, M., & Scholl, L. (forthcoming) construct an inventory of “financing instruments” for nature-based solutions. This inventory is broader than our definition of rewarding mechanisms, and the focus is on ponds/capscapes/landscapes and nature-based solutions, rather than our narrower focus on farms; however, the

inventory provides a useful overview of financing instruments (including rewarding mechanisms) and their strengths and weaknesses, as well as some relevant examples.

This initial list will be supplemented through the study.

3. Definition and categorization of rewarding mechanisms

3.1. Definition of rewarding mechanisms

Rewarding mechanisms for climate-friendly agricultural actions on emission reductions, carbon removals or climate adaptation are rewarding farmers in return for implementing a desired action or delivering a desired outcome and can be sourced from public or private entities or a mix of both and include regulatory obligations, voluntary public funds, R&D, voluntary carbon markets and price premiums/labelling.

3.2. Scope of climate action

There is a wide range of climate action on plot, field and landscape level on EU agricultural land, which are captured to varying degrees in the different existing or planned rewarding mechanisms. They can be grouped into: 1) emission reduction which are mainly methane (CH₄) from enteric fermentation and N₂O emissions from managed agricultural soils, which together represent over 80% of agricultural emission in the EU. Other sources of emissions include CH₄ from manure management, soil carbon emissions from organic and mineral soils. 2) the removal of CO₂ from the atmosphere by converting between land cover types and managing the agricultural soils to increase carbon sequestration and 3) the response to climate change by increasing the adaptive capacity of the agricultural sector.

The rewarding mechanisms have to be applied or applicable in the EU and excludes forestry and the upstream and downstream sector.

3.3. Source of rewarding

Rewarding sources can be divided into two main categories: Public rewarding and private rewarding. Both can include monetary and non-monetary rewards, while most of the existing mechanisms involve monetary funding. With public rewarding we refer to funding or aid from the international community, EU, State or regional level e.g. Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), R&D programs, etc. Private rewarding can mean any type of funding from the private sector (companies, private organisations, and consumers) through carbon markets or price premiums and labels. There are also public/private funding sources such as market-based approaches where the Government plays a central role providing or distributing the funding.

In this report we are assessing the public and private rewarding options as well as a combination of both including non-monetary rewards.

3.4. Rewarding method

There are various options for rewarding farmers and land users for their climate action. Overall, they can be distinguished between the delivery of action-based or result based outcomes.

Action-based funding provides rewarding to the farmer in compliance with usually very specific farming practices. Farmer or landowner receives a payment or reward for implementing defined management actions, independently of the resulting impact of those actions (COWI et al. 2021) Action-based models are commonly used in the EU and Member States as part of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). This method comes along with advantages and challenges described below (based on Life Carbon Farming Scheme 2021):

Advantages:

- In general, the farmer receives the money immediately after completing the climate action. This reduces the farmers uncertainty about receiving support.
- This rewarding method can be tailored to consider individual characteristics of the different measures, and local conditions (e.g. weather, climate, soil structure, landscape, etc).

Challenges:

- Action-based rewarding has no direct link to the actual outcome. Hence, there is an uncertainty whether the result will be generated at all, bringing farmers into a defensive crouch.
- The action-based model is less suitable for certain types of climate action (e.g. Carbon removals/ carbon markets), if public or private entities want to pay for the carbon sequestered.

Result-based funding is tied to a verified outcome and requires a direct link and explicit link between the result delivered (e.g. Emission reduced/avoided, carbon sequestered) and the reward that the farmer receives. Again, this method comes along with advantages and challenges described below (based on COWI et al. 2021):

Advantages:

- Clearer link between reward for the farmer and outcome/climate impact which leads to a higher credibility of the climate action.
- Potential for higher additionality.

Challenges:

- Potential higher risks and uncertainty for farmers because climate action does not necessarily lead to the wished outcome.
- Potential higher transaction costs for farmers and project developers
- Challenges related to monitoring, reporting and verification (MRV) of climate action results (costs, degree of reliability/ robustness).
- Challenges of ensuring additionality and of securing long-term climate impacts.
- Low signal to noise ratio when rewarding carbon removal activities which can lead to long lifespan of change.
- Strong advisory support is needed to be built into reward design. however, capacity or resources for this may be lacking.

3.5. Types of on-farm climate actions

Farmers or land-users have to deliver certain on-farm climate actions to receive the reward. This can include e.g. livestock emission reductions, peatland emission reduction, fertilizer emission reductions, agroforestry, soil carbon, manure storage, reduced livestock, climate adaptation and the co-benefits connected to climate actions.

3.6. Time of rewarding

There are different design options on the timing of rewarding e.g. when and how often the rewarding is happening. Ex-ante rewarding is a rewarding (usually monetary) before the climate action has occurred. However, first the project needs to be certified or registered and the climate action assessed by an independent auditor. This payment model can be relevant for long-term projects, which need substantial upfront investments, while the actual climate action outcome can take years (I4CE 2019). Ex-post rewarding is done after the climate action has been produced by the farmer. The rewarding can be one off or ongoing/multi-year rewarding during the project timeline. Also combinations of the time of rewarding is possible. Ex-ante and ex-post rewarding come along with advantages and challenges described below (based on The World Bank 2018).

Ex-ante rewarding:

Advantages:

- Simple method from a technical perspective.
- Initial investment for financing the climate action.

Challenges:

- Weaker incentives for farmers and donor of reward (especially the private sector), because it does not reward performance.
- Risk of giving up the good practice after the reward has taken place.
- Equity concerns: A key challenge is how to determine an equitable allocation of funds.

Ex-post rewarding:

Advantages:

- Potential for higher incentives because certain stakeholders may respond well to rewards linked to performance (especially the private sector)

Challenges:

- Risk of non-performance by the farmer and in consequence loss of potential rewards

Table 1: Assessment tree of rewarding mechanisms for climate-friendly nature based agricultural action (DRAFT)

Assessment tree of rewarding mechanisms for climate-friendly nature based agricultural action

4. Case Studies

Based on the categorization of rewarding mechanism successful examples of rewarding mechanisms and their outcomes will be assessed, at least one of each type of climate action (10-20 examples in total). Before assessing the rewarding mechanisms, a fiche template will be developed to ensure consistent collection of information. See below the methodology of the selection of case studies and a draft of the fiche template.

4.1. Methodology

The WP6 partners will come up with a list of case studies to be assessed as part of task 6.2. In addition, a survey will be sent to the CFD network to ask for additional rewarding mechanisms to be considered. This process will lead to a long list of rewarding mechanisms. Out of this long list of rewarding mechanisms a short list of around 10-20 case studies will be selected based on two criteria: 1) coverage of different scopes and categorization types of rewarding mechanisms (ch. 3) and 2) good quality of information available. The assessment of selected rewarding mechanisms are completed based on programmed documents and desk research.

4.2. Selection of case studies by WP6 partners

Public:

- CAP Basic income payments
- CAP eco-schemes (2023-2027) – include 3 MS examples
- CAP Rural Development measures (2023-2027) – include 3 examples
- He Waka Eke Noa – NZ Emission Levy deduction³
- Australian Emission Reduction Fund – Estimation of soil organic carbon sequestration using measurement and models method⁴

Private:

- Gold Standard - Soil Organic Carbon Framework Methodology⁵ – Carbon Removal
- Verra – Methodology for Improved Agricultural Land Management⁶ - Emission Reduction and Carbon Removal
- German Tierhaltungskennzeichnung (animal welfare label) - Labelling
- Label bas Carbone – Carbon Agri⁷ - Carbon Removal
- MoorFutures Standard⁸ - Emission Reduction
- ARLA Climate Check – Reward within the supply chain?
- EU Organic Farming – Climate adaptation

³ <https://hewakaekenoa.nz/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/FINAL-He-Waka-Eke-Noa-Recommendations-Report.pdf>

⁴ <https://www.cleanenergyregulator.gov.au/DocumentAssets/Documents/Understanding%20your%20soil%20carbon%20project%20-%20Simple%20method%20guide.pdf>

⁵ <https://www.goldstandard.org/project-developers/standard-documents>

⁶ https://verra.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/VM0042_Methodology-for-Improved-Agricultural-Land-Management_v1.0.pdf

⁷ <https://www.france-carbon-agri.fr/methodologie-carbon-agri/>

⁸ https://www.moorfutures.de/app/download/27884071/Moorfutures_Standard.pdf

- A Life Carbon Farming project?

Missing case studies to be asked specifically in the survey to the CFD network:

- Two more case studies on Climate adaption
- Two more case studies on non-monetary rewards
- One more case study on rewarding through the supply chain

4.3. Draft fiche template

Table 2: draft fiche template to collect information on the rewarding mechanism

Rewarding mechanism name:			
Summary	Short summary of key design elements of the rewarding mechanisms (location, years operational, scope incentivised)		
Type of climate action	Carbon removal	Emission reduction/ avoidance	Climate adaptation
Appropriate for: Who can use this type of rewarding mechanism	e.g. Farmers/Landowners, Other entities		
Source of rewarding: Who provides the rewarding?	Public	Private	Public-Private
Rewarding method: What is the rewarding based on?	e.g. action based, result based, mixed		
Incentive: How are recipients incentivized?	e.g. offsets, public payments, contribution claims, labelling, farm advisory		
Type of on-farm action: What is the project obliged to deliver in return?	Description of the on-farm climate action to be delivered to receive the rewarding e.g. livestock emission reductions, soil carbon, etc		
Recipient requirements: What requirements must recipients meet to receive finance?	e.g. any conditions around recipient type, size, location etc.		
Time of rewarding: When is the reward happening?	e.g. ex ante, ex-post		

<p>Rewarding timeline: How often is the reward happening?</p>	<p>e.g. one off, ongoing, multi-year payment</p>
<p>Type of rewarding: Is the rewarding monetary or non-monetary?</p>	<p>e.g. monetary, non-monetary</p>
<p>Effectiveness: What is the climate objective and to what extent is it achieved?</p>	<p>e.g. MRV standards for quantification</p>
<p>Efficiency: Is the outcome achieved at low cost?</p>	<p>e.g. Administrative costs and difficulties / farmers costs and difficulties</p>
<p>Equity: Are there equity concerns?</p>	<p>e.g. who can participate (only large farms/ small farms)</p>
<p>Co-benefits: Does the rewarding mechanism deliver co-benefits?</p>	<p>e.g. benefits for biodiversity, soil, water</p>
<p>Governance: How does governance behind the mechanisms look like?</p>	<p>e.g. Governance procedures, roles, regulatory requirements</p>
<p>References:</p>	<p>References</p>

5. Fiche CAP basic income support

Table 3: CAP basic income support - draft fiche

Rewarding mechanism name: CAP basic income support			
Summary	Short summary of key design elements of the rewarding mechanisms (location, years operational, scope incentivised)		
Type of climate action	Carbon removal	Emission reduction/avoidance	climate adaptation
Appropriate for: Who can use this type of rewarding mechanism	Farmers in the EU that are able to comply with the mandatory rules (known as “enhanced conditionality”), comprising so called Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions (GAECs).		
Source of rewarding: Who provides the rewarding?	Public	<i>Private</i>	<i>Public-Private</i>
Rewarding method: What is the rewarding based on?	Action based. If farmers comply with the mandatory rules, they are able to receive the basic income support.		
Incentive: How are recipients incentivized?	public payments for delivering minimum standards		
Type of on-farm action: What is the project obliged to deliver in return?	The enhanced conditionality comprises the so called GAEC standards which include maintenance of permanent grassland (GAEC 1), protection of wetland and peatland (GAEC 2), establishment of buffer strips along water courses (GAEC 4), tillage management (GAEC 5), minimum soil cover (GAEC 6), crop rotation/diversification (GAEC 7), fallow land (GAEC 8) and ESPG in Natura2000 (GAEC9).		
Recipient requirements: What requirements must recipients meet to receive finance?	In accordance with EU law, the enhanced conditionality sets out the basic requirements ("baseline") that farmers must fulfil in order to receive the basic income support or to be able to apply for additional voluntary CAP support. The enhanced conditionality includes, statutory management requirements (SMR) and standards for good agricultural and environmental conditions of land (GAEC).		

Time of rewarding: When is the reward happening?	Ex-post
Rewarding timeline: How often is the reward happening?	<i>e.g. one off, ongoing, multi-year payment</i>
Type of rewarding: Is the rewarding monetary or non-monetary?	Monetary
Effectiveness: What is the climate objective and to what extent is it achieved?	<i>e.g. MRV standards for quantification</i>
Efficiency: Is the outcome achieved at low cost?	<i>e.g. Administrative costs and difficulties / farmers costs and difficulties</i>
Equity: Are there equity concerns?	<i>e.g. who can participate (only large farms/ small farms)</i>
Co-benefits: Does the rewarding mechanism deliver co-benefits?	<i>e.g. benefits for biodiversity, soil, water</i>
Governance: How does governance behind the mechanisms look like?	<i>e.g. Governance procedures, roles, regulatory requirements</i>
References:	<i>References</i>

6. Research questions

As part of the deliverables of task 6.2. research questions will come up that need to be discussed. In this section we want to outline potential research questions to be discussed as part of the deliverable of task 6.2.

- **Removals equivalence:** Is it ok – and under what conditions – to substitute removals for emissions reductions in the AFOLU context?
- **Missing rewarding mechanisms:** Looking at the categorization of mechanisms. Are there any areas, with no or only few rewarding mechanisms in place (e.g. Climate adaptation, reduction of cost instead of additional funding)?
- **Differentiation between short- and long-lived gas emissions:** Should there be differences in rewarding, depending on the type of gas (CH₄, N₂O, CO₂)?

7. Timeline, planning

Date	What	Who
23.01.23	Outline of deliverable, timeline, and responsibilities	Aaron
24.01.23	Feedback from partners	Partners
March 23	Revision of outline	Aaron
March 23	Second round of feedback from partners	Partners
16/05	Task 6.2 Milestone deliverable: Assessment Framework	EI
May 23	Draft outline for survey	EI
1 st June 23	Finalize survey and send around	EI
9/06	Online mid-term annual meeting: Short intro of the survey	EI
Summer 23	Assessment and describing of case studies Assessing survey results	EI with support from Partners
Autumn /Winter 23	1 st Policy Brief on first results of assessment	EI, ELO
September 2025	Report on state of the art of existing and emerging rewarding mechanism – final deliverable	EI

8. References

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